

A Deep Learning Framework for RSRP Prediction Using Image-Based Geospatial Features

Athanasios Manassas ⁽¹⁾, Spyridon Delidimitriou ⁽¹⁾, and Theodoros Samaras ⁽²⁾

(1) Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation (CIRI), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

(2) Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

Abstract— The objective of this study is to predict the Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) in a real urban environment using neural networks trained exclusively on real measurement data and grayscale image-based features. Each image represents a localized urban environment, where the RSRP measurement point is placed at the image center. The surrounding region includes spatial features such as buildings, roads, macrocell antennas (MAs), and small cell antennas (SCAs). To enable the neural networks to learn the spatial dependencies of signal propagation, building and antenna heights were encoded using distinct grayscale intensity levels, since these structural characteristics strongly influence signal attenuation, as buildings can act as obstacles between transmitting antennas and measurement points. Two datasets were developed, differing in how the spatial features were represented as input data: the first consists of single composite images that merge all spatial features into one channel, while the second adopts a multi-channel format, where each channel represents a distinct feature type (buildings, MAs, SCAs, and roads).

I. INTRODUCTION

Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) is a fundamental metric in LTE and 5G systems, reflecting large-scale propagation effects such as path loss and shadowing. Accurate RSRP prediction is essential for coverage assessment, network optimization, and exposure analysis. Traditional empirical and deterministic propagation models rely on simplified assumptions and often struggle to generalize across heterogeneous urban environments. Recent advances in artificial intelligence have enabled data-driven approaches that learn propagation behavior directly from measurements [1]. In this work, we investigate an image-based deep learning framework that leverages GIS-derived spatial representations to predict RSRP in a dense urban setting using exclusively real-world measurement data.

II. MEASUREMENT CAMPAIGN AND DATASET

RSRP measurements were collected in July 2025 in the city center of Thessaloniki using three identical smartphones, each connected to a different mobile network operator, operating on 4G LTE networks. Measurements were obtained using the G-NetTrack application, recording geographic coordinates, timestamps, and RSRP values for serving and neighboring cells. The total RSRP per operator was computed by summing the reported RSRP values at each location, yielding approximately 20,000 samples with an average spatial spacing of 3.5 m.

To generate spatial inputs, building and road layers were imported from OpenStreetMap (OSM) into QGIS (an open-source geographic information system), while base station locations and installation heights were obtained from the Hellenic Telecommunications and Post Commission database [2]. For each RSRP measurement, a 256×256 pixel image corresponding to a 384×384 m area was generated and centered on the measurement point.

III. IMAGE ENCODING AND MODEL ARCHITECTURES

Spatial features were generated using a GIS-based pipeline. Building and road layers were imported into QGIS from OSM datasets, while base station locations and installation heights for all Greek mobile network operators were obtained from the official EETT database [2] and verified through manual inspection using Google Maps and on-site validation. Since both building height and antenna height strongly affect signal attenuation, these parameters were explicitly encoded in the generated images. For buildings lacking height information in OSM, the number of floors was manually recorded and converted to height assuming a representative floor height of 3 m. Although antenna power and gain information were available in the EETT database, these fields were often incomplete and were therefore excluded. Instead, base stations were classified as macrocells (MAs) or small cells (SCAs), a distinction that implicitly reflects significant differences in transmission power and is reliably provided by the database.

Two image-based input representations were evaluated (Fig. 1). In the single-channel approach, buildings, roads, MAs, and SCAs were fused into a single grayscale image centered on each RSRP measurement point. Building heights were encoded using grayscale intensities proportional to height, while MAs and SCAs were represented as circular markers with distinct intensity ranges reflecting antenna height and cell type. In the multi-channel approach, each feature type (buildings, MAs, SCAs, and roads) was provided as a separate grayscale channel, enabling the CNN to learn feature-specific spatial patterns independently.

Two convolutional neural network architectures were implemented. A baseline CNN composed of four convolutional blocks followed by global average pooling and fully connected layers was trained using the Adam optimizer and mean squared error loss. In addition, a deeper ResNet-type CNN [3] with bottleneck residual blocks was evaluated using the Huber loss function [4] to improve robustness to outliers. Prior to training, RSRP outliers were removed using a 3σ criterion, duplicate coordinates and incomplete records were discarded, and RSRP values were normalized per operator to mitigate device-

dependent offsets. To prevent spatial data leakage, the dataset was partitioned into training (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%) subsets using K-means clustering on geographic coordinates, ensuring that each subset corresponded to spatially disjoint urban regions (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Example CNN inputs for RSRP prediction. (a) Single-channel fused map combining buildings, roads, and base stations; the central white dot marks the RSRP measurement point. (b) Four-channel representation showing buildings, roads, MAs, and SCAs.

Figure 2. Map of the RSRP measurement routes in Thessaloniki showing training (green), validation (blue), and test (red) routes.

IV. RESULTS

Both models achieved comparable accuracy on the test dataset (Table I), with the baseline CNN using single-channel inputs yielding the lowest overall error (MAE = 8.93 dB, RMSE = 11.37 dB).

The ResNet-type CNN trained with the four-channel images achieved performance comparable to the other models on the test set but exhibited a significantly lower MAE on the training data (MAE = 3.03 dB after 59 epochs) (Fig. 3), indicating a higher fitting capacity and a tendency toward overfitting. The low training MAE demonstrates that the model is capable of effectively learning complex relationships within the data. With a larger and more representative dataset, the same model could likely achieve improved generalization and lower test error.

TABLE I. TEST PERFORMANCE OF BASELINE AND RESNET-TYPE CNN MODELS.

Model	Input type	Test MAE (dB)	Test RMSE (dB)
Baseline CNN	Single channel	8.93	11.37
	Four channel	9.94	12.50
ResNet-type CNN	Single channel	9.05	11.44
	Four channel	9.70	12.22

Figure 3. Training and validation MAE (dBm) over epochs for the ResNet-type CNN (four-channel input; early stopping at epoch 59).

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates a measurement-driven, image-based deep learning framework for predicting RSRP in a real urban environment. Real multi-operator RSRP measurements were used to construct standardized geospatial images integrating environmental and network infrastructure features derived from OSM and ETT databases. Two input representations—single-channel composite images and multi-channel feature-separated images—were evaluated and achieved comparable predictive performance. While the ResNet-type architecture exhibited higher fitting capacity, it also showed a tendency toward overfitting, suggesting that improved generalization may require a larger and more diverse dataset, stronger regularization, and richer propagation-aware features.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Funding for this research was provided by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Framework Programme under Grant Agreement number 101057622 (SEAWave Project).

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Feng, Z. Meng, L. Wei, and L. Zhang, “A recent survey on radio map estimation methods for wireless networks,” *Electronics*, vol. 14, no. 8, Art. no. 1564, 2025, doi: 10.3390/electronics14081564.
- [2] Hellenic Telecommunications and Post Commission (ETT), “Antenna Information System,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://keraies.eett.gr>. Accessed: Oct. 27, 2025.
- [3] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, “Deep residual learning for image recognition,” in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR)*, 2016, pp. 770–778, doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2016.90.
- [4] P. J. Huber, “Robust estimation of a location parameter,” *Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 73–101, 1964, doi: 10.1214/aoms/1177703732.